

THE SEMIOTIC TRANSFORMATION: A.REVATHI'S KANNADA TRANSLATED TRANSGENDER AUTOBIOGRAPHY "BADUKU BAYALU" FROM TEXT TO THEATRE PERFORMANCE

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Abstract

There are many transgender Autobiographies which talks about their life. They expressed through writing. A. Revathi's literary pieces namely, The Truth About Me: A Hijra Life Story (2010) she not only written but performed to express her inner turmoil. The purpose of this study is to attempt to evaluate semiotic transformation in A. Revathi's kannada translated autobiography "Baduku Bayalu," from text to theatre performance. Semiotic means "meaning-making activity," The study of signs and symbols as a crucial component of communication is explored in the semiotic act. Here, A.Revathi acted out her own life after seeing a performance of it on stage. The idea and choice to portray her life on stage represents a significant semantic change. Her theatrical performance left a lasting impression on the audience. A. Revathi discussed this in her interview prior to the performance, mentioning how people's perceptions of her changed as a result. She thought it was the most effective medium to use.

Keywords: *transgender, autobiography, theatre, semiotic, performance*

Introduction

Autobiographies are first person account of a person's life written by that person itself. Writers use autobiography as a form to express themselves clearly and deeply. Autobiographies provide a platform for the readers to understand and evaluate writers more intensely. Many suppressed classes like women, untouchables, and transgender make use of autobiographies to reveal their trauma to the public and thereby calling for a change in their discriminated status

Transgender study, a school of critical discourse that branched out from queer LGBT studies focuses on the transgender people. Transgender is often used to refer to people who do not adapt to the prevailing expectations concerning gender. They identify themselves with and live the genders that were not assigned to them at birth. They live and present themselves in those gender behaviors that may not be readily intelligible in terms of traditional conceptions of gender. Like all the other subcultural sexual minorities, transgenders also experience oppression and marginalization in multiple modalities. The dominant discourse on sexuality has forced such people to live as sexual subalterns relegated to a space outside.

There are many studies on transgender autobiographies, studied with the common factor that the research more concentrated on transgender internal and external turmoil and struggle, and socio-cultural aspects through autobiographies. It includes how they are vulnerable and discriminated against inhumanely. Even Society is not ready to accept them as normal human beings. Their rituals, traditions, and customs are quite different from the rest of the society. Many of them raised their voices through writing and became activists working for their rights. There are many works done on these factors, but there are still many facts that require attention.

The suggested study takes a semiotic approach to analyze A.Revathi's autobiography on contemporary Kannada theatre. Man is a social creature who lives according to his own way; as such, he needs some form of entertainment in his life. He satisfies his aspirations by engaging in theatre, film, folk art, etc. Drama is a strong instrument to influence society, as we all know. It's not just for fun. Famous playwrights and theatre professionals also use drama as a potent tool to address social issues in many different worlds. Drama has gained technical sophistication and had a significant social impact as a result of this process. Drama has an impact on cross-cultural interactions, societal ideologies, and ideas between the east and west.

Likewise, transgender autobiographies A Revathi is a writer, activist, and actor. Her autobiography "The Truth About Me: A Hijra Life Story" (2010) talks about her sense of "being in the wrong body" along with that physical violence and sexual abuse. V. Geetha's initial translation from Tamil into English was made available by Penguin Books. Then U Sarasvathi translated it as "Baduku Bayalu" in Kannada in 2019.

The Journey from he to she

A. Revathi was initially called as Doraisamy. He born as the youngest male sibling in the family of three brothers and a sister. he as the body of a male was expected

to behave like a male by the heteronormative society, But his male body nurtured the desires and passions of being a female“. He/she (?) always felt that a woman is trapped within a man’s body:

A woman trapped in a man’s body was how I thought of myself... I wondered why God had chose to inflict this peculiar torture on me, and why He could not have created me wholly male or wholly female. Why am I a flawed being, I wondered often... and all the time I was obsessed, confused and anxious. (15)

Revathi in the autobiography narrates multiple incidences that how passionately Doraisamy wanted to dress like a woman and how he/she (?) enjoyed playing the role of female characters on stage during the school annual day celebration or how he/she (?) enjoyed putting on the “Female disguise”(16) during the celebration of the Mariamman festival in her village:

As soon as I got home from school, I would wear my sister’s long skirt and blouse, twist a long towel around my head and let it trail down my back like a braid. I would then walk as if I was a shy bride, my eyes to the ground [...]”(4)

“In class, I would sit staring at the girls, taking note of the way their braids fell, the intricate knot of their colorful ribbons, the jasmine and kanakambaram they wore in their hair, and their skirts and blouses. I longed to be like them and suffered that I could not dress so.” (6) “I played Chandramathi in Harishchandra [...] I think I did this exceptionally well, because everyone praised me saying that I Looked and acted like a real woman. This pleased me very much.” (9) “In my kurathi’s garb, I could express all those female feelings that I usually have to suppress and so felt happy [...] I had not worn a disguise I said to myself; I had given form to my real feelings.” (14-16)

Thus, dress “being one of the major and perhaps the most important marker of heteronormative gender distinction, cross dressing is regarded as the primary source of desire fulfillment by the transgender community.

Revathi portrays the crippled identity of a human being, who has faced the non-cultural acceptance from the Indian society. This limitation of cultural construction of gender has paved way to ponder the significance of psyche for the decision making. Here the choice of the transgender identity paves the way to construct her own identity.

Revathi decided to live a woman's life. This construction of a woman identity is crucial, the society has to accept her as a woman, it is next to impossible. But the boldness in Revathi has made her woman identity with the physical transformation.

After transformation, Revathi more interested in leading a family life, with husband and children. She knows her bodily limitations. So Adoption was another option which is in front of her. Every woman has a mother in herself, whether she delivers a child or not is not the matter.

“I knew I couldn't have biological children (...), after all isn't it motherhood all about being nurturing and caring?” (ALITA 39-40).

The real woman in Revathi has made her to take a decision of bringing up a child. Fortunately she got three daughters, who were males before and castrated themselves to females. She presented her identity as a woman.

From Activist to performer

Janamanadata Heggodu, a modern theatre that promotes equality and fraternity, has taken on the task of adapting this autobiography. It was presented in narrative form by an Indian theatre company. This was the first Hijra-related Kannada play to be performed live on stage. In order to specifically examine A. Revathi's autobiography "Baduku Bayalu," which was translated into Kannada, this study adopts a semiotic perspective.

A Revathi in an interview with **Mittal Institute** Said,

“When I went to see it for the first time it was their 49th performance, and I got goosebumps as I watched my life experiences play out before my eyes. That is when I realized how immediately theater can touch the hearts of the public. That drama group included me in their work, and I began educating people through the arts. Subsequently, there were over 100 stage performances of Baduku Bayalu across Karnataka from 2013 to 2014.”

“Since then, I have been acting Vellai Mozhi as a Tamil monologue in India and abroad and have completed 112 stage performances to date. I am currently conducting this drama for public school students across Tamil Nadu. Along with sharing my experiences with the students and instilling within them a sense of the importance of education, I create an environment in the minds of the students in which there is no differentiation based on caste, religion, or race.”

In contemporary theatre, apart from the written script, directors are attempting drama, fiction, and poetry by using the narration form. For any text, we have readers in the same way that, for performance, we have an audience. We are in the technological era. We will get e-books and audio books as well. In the same way, today, theatre is also the main tool to reach many hearts. Most of the reviews here resemble transgender internal and external turmoil in general.

Semiotics

Semiotics is the study of how signs and symbols create meaning within a text, exploring the relationship between signifiers means words, images and signifieds it mean the concepts they represents. It delves into the layers of meaning embedded in language and other symbolic systems. It helps readers understand not only what a text says, but how it says it and the cultural context it reflects.

This research adopts semiotics as a methodology to carry out this particular research and its analysis. The concept of "theatre semiotics' has already been established to explore socio cultural and literary perceptions and understandings. The famous Italian philosopher, semiotician, and fiction writer Umberto Eco rightly pointed out, that "every human activity is a semiotic act. This proposition substantiates this research to analyse the influence of A. Revathi's Kannada translated autobiography " Baduku Bayalu" from text to theatre performance.

Therefore, since the theatre is also one of the socio cultural sign systems, this intends to adopt semiotics as a major methodological criterion for this research. Specifically speaking, the drama text, director, a group of actors, technicians, and spectators are also part of this sign system. The significance of the semiotic approach to understanding theatre is how important, as discussed by Roland Barthes. According to Roland Barthes 'view of the theatrical sign as part of an alterable system of signification, Brecht's understanding is calling attention to the machinery of signification and thus to the contractedness of the theatrical sign as well as of the culture that produced it, hoped to bring his audience to realise that both sign and culture were thus not natural and inevitable but susceptible to change.

Conclusion

The theatre performance will change the attitude towards strange opinions about transgenders. Theater as a powerful tool is changing public opinion about the life of a transgender person. The status of transgender people in the premises of social construction, they are considered normal like others. Theatre not just narrates story; by educating people with art in the service of others, art is a powerful tool that can be used to make people think. Transgender people too have reservations about education and occupation. It helps in making policy for the transgender community. It will inspire NGOs to work on it and lobby the government.

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